

ENGLISH PROFICIENCY AS PREDICTOR OF ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE OF GRADE 1 LEARNERS

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English Proficiency as Predictor of Academic Performance of Grade 1 Learners

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Abstract

This study aimed to determine the level of English proficiency as predictor of academic performance of Grade 1 learners in East Maitum District. This study employed quantitative research design utilizing descriptive survey. The respondents of this study were the 194 Grade 1 learners from the 6 different elementary schools in East Maitum District. The following conclusions were established and formulated based on the results of the study: First, the level of English proficiency of learners was high in terms of spelling skills and writing skills, while moderately high in terms of grammar skills. Second, the majority of the learners obtained a very satisfactory academic performance. Lastly, the domains that predict the academic performance of Grade 1 learners were the spelling and writing skills. Nevertheless, English proficiency enabled learners to comprehend and effectively engage with course materials, participate in class discussions, and produce written assignments with clarity and precision, thus fostering success in their academic endeavors.

Keywords: *educational management, english proficiency, grade 1 learners, descriptive survey, philippines*

Introduction

One of the global issues impacting learners' academic performance is the lack of access to quality early childhood education. Many children, particularly those from disadvantaged backgrounds or in developing countries, faced barriers such as limited availability of preschools, inadequate resources, and untrained teachers. This lack of early educational experiences resulted in an achievement gap that persisted throughout their academic journey. Additionally, socio-economic factors, language barriers, and insufficient support systems further contributed to challenges in learners' academic performance, highlighting the need for targeted interventions and investments to guarantee everyone to have fair access to high-quality education (Al-Busaidi, 2021; Alrasheed et al., 2021; Stoffelsma & Spooren, 2019).

However, examining students' academic achievement is crucial because it explains how well instructional strategies, educational institutions, and student support systems work. By examining multiple factors that impact academic performance, including instructional strategies, curriculum development, learning environments, and student attributes, scholars and practitioners can pinpoint opportunities for enhancement, execute empirically supported interventions, and customize pedagogical approaches to cater to the heterogeneous needs of students. This research helps foster educational equity, enhance student outcomes, and inform policy decisions that promote a high-quality and inclusive education system for all learners (Nair & Kulkarni, 2020; Üzümlü & Pesen, 2019).

However, English proficiency and the academic performance of Grade 1 learners are significant as they directly impact their ability to comprehend, communicate, and engage with various subject areas. Proficiency in English enables learners to understand instructions, read texts, and effectively express their thoughts and ideas, facilitating their learning and participation in classroom activities. Strong English skills also contribute to developing foundational literacy and language abilities, which are crucial for success across academic disciplines. Moreover, English proficiency opens doors to accessing educational resources, expanding vocabulary, and building critical thinking skills, ultimately enhancing the overall academic performance of Grade 1 learners (Cocca & Cocca, 2019; Kadwa & Alshenqeti, 2020; Mirza, 2020).

On the other hand, identified Grade 1 learners in East Maitum District needed better levels of English proficiency, focusing on their writing skills. This matter dramatically affected their academic performance. If learners master English proficiency skills, they would improve their learning and gain confidence in participating and presenting their ideas in class. Conducting a research study on English proficiency as a predictor of the academic performance of Grade 1 learners was urgently needed due to its potential impact on educational equity and student outcomes. By exploring the relationship between English proficiency and academic performance at an early stage, researchers can identify specific areas of improvement and develop targeted interventions to support students who may be struggling. This research can inform educational policies, curriculum development, and instructional strategies to ensure that grade 1 learners receive the necessary language support and resources for their academic success, ultimately fostering a more inclusive and effective educational system. Hence, the researcher aimed to conduct this study to determine the proficiency level of Grade 1 learners, focusing on their writing skills. The researcher wanted to determine their academic performance and the domain of writing skills that significantly could influence their academic performance. This study was conducted in East Maitum district, Division of Sarangani, for the school year 2022-2023.

Research Objectives

This study aimed to determine the level of English proficiency as a predictor of academic performance of Grade 1 learners in East Maitum District. Specifically, the following objectives were formulated:

1. To determine the level of English proficiency that predicts the academic performance among Grade 1 learners focusing on writing skills in terms of:
 - 1.1. vocabulary;
 - 1.2. writing; and
 - 1.3. spelling.
2. To focus on writing skills to determine the academic performance of Grade 1 learners in English.
3. To determine the significant relationship between English proficiency level and academic performance of Grade 1 learners.
4. To determine the domain in English proficiency that predicts the academic performance of Grade 1 learners.

Methodology

This section depicts the various methods of the study, including research design, research locale, population and sample, research instruments used to measure constructs of interest, data collection procedures, and statistical tools.

Research Design

This study employed a non-experimental quantitative research approach and utilized specifically descriptive-correlational technique. Quantitative research aims to quantify the process of gathering and analyzing data. It is derived from a deductive method emphasizing theory testing and influenced by positivist and empiricist ideologies. Quantitative research design aims to collect numerical data and extrapolate it to other demographics. Every aspect of this design is meticulously and precisely prepared before data collection, and the researcher has a well-defined research issue for which objective solutions are sought. Examples of data are numerical data and statistics (Leavy, 2022; Rahman, 2020).

In quantitative research, closed-ended questions are frequently preferred. Respondents are given a predetermined list of options to provide in-depth, open-ended responses. This design ensures that the quantitative research process is much more effective than if open-ended questions of the qualitative type were used. It is more effective because it eliminates the need for the time-consuming task of coding a sizable number of open-ended responses (Swart et al., 2019).

Moreover, quantitative research is a systematic and structured approach to investigating a research question or phenomenon using numerical data and statistical analysis. It involves collecting data through standardized instruments such as surveys or experiments and analyzing it using statistical methods to identify patterns, relationships, and statistical trends. Quantitative research aims to generate objective and generalizable findings by gathering data from representative samples and making statistical inferences about the broader population (Cooksey & Cooksey, 2020; Habib, 2021).

Similarly, quantitative research involves structured and rigorous data collection and analysis. Researchers use well-defined research questions or hypotheses and carefully design studies to ensure the reliability and validity of the findings. The data collected in quantitative research is typically numerical, allowing for objective measurement and statistical analysis. It enables researchers to quantify relationships, determine the strength of associations, and make comparisons between variables or groups. The data in quantitative research is often gathered using various methods such as surveys, questionnaires, experiments, or existing datasets. Researchers aim to collect data from a representative sample that is sufficiently large to provide meaningful results (Sürücü & Maslacki, 2020).

On the other hand, descriptive research provides a detailed and systematic understanding of a phenomenon, aiming to accurately define the population, market, or circumstances under investigation. This approach is widely used across various fields to gather comprehensive and relevant information, employing both quantitative and qualitative data to offer a holistic view. Quantitative data, such as statistical analyses and numerical metrics, allows for precise measurement and comparison, while qualitative data, such as interviews and open-ended surveys, provides context and depth to the findings. Descriptive survey research, a common technique within this methodology, involves directly engaging with subjects to quickly and effectively gather data pertinent to the research goals (Millner et al., 2020).

Further, a descriptive survey research design gathers information about a population's characteristics, behaviors, opinions, attitudes, or a specific group. This type of research design aims to provide a detailed description of the studied subject rather than testing a specific hypothesis or making a causal relationship between variables. In order to get information on the issue, descriptive survey research designs often use questionnaires, interviews, or other data-gathering techniques. The analysis and presentation of the data gathered subsequently provide a thorough summary of the topic under study. This type of study design is frequently employed in psychology, market research, and social sciences (Sürücü & Maslacki, 2020).

Furthermore, descriptive survey research design is quantitative research that describes a population or group's characteristics. This design aims to provide a detailed and accurate portrayal of the subject under investigation rather than testing a specific hypothesis or making predictions about cause-and-effect relationships. Descriptive surveys may collect data on various topics such as demographics, social attitudes, opinions, behaviors, and lifestyles. Descriptive survey research design may involve sampling techniques such as random or stratified sampling to ensure that the sample represents the studied population (Millner et al., 2020).

Participants

This study's respondents were 194 Grade 1 learners from the six elementary schools of East Maitum District. There were 31 learners from Malalag Central Elementary School, 34 from Kiayap Elementary School, 32 from Maitum Elementary School, 30 from Sison Elementary School, 36 from Virginia Tanedo-Garcia Elementary School, and 31 from Pangí Elementary School. Total enumeration refers to the process of systematically counting and recording every individual or item within a defined population or area, ensuring comprehensive data collection without sampling. This method is commonly used in censuses and large-scale surveys to achieve precise and accurate information about the entire population (Morse, 2021).

The researcher set the inclusion criteria for the respondents: male or female, regardless of religion and ethnicity, ages 6-7, who were currently enrolled as Grade 1 learners in any of the school from Malalag Central Elementary School, Kiayap Elementary School, Maitum Elementary School, Sison Elementary School, Virginia Tanedo-Garcia Elementary School, and Pangí Elementary School. Conversely, specific individuals were excluded from this study, including Grade 1 learners ages five and above eight years old. Additionally, respondents who were unable or unwilling to consent or cooperate in data collection were excluded from the study. Nevertheless, respondents had the right to withdraw from the study at any stage without providing a reason. Any respondent who chose to withdraw was assured that their decision would not have any negative consequences or impact on their relationship with the school or program. Furthermore, if any respondents displayed discomfort, distress, or emotional unease during the study, appropriate measures were taken to support and ensure their well-being.

Table 1. *The Distribution of the Respondents*

<i>Schools</i>	<i>Number of Respondents</i>
Malalag Central Elementary School	31
Kiayap Elementary School	34
Maitum Elementary School	32
Sison Elementary School	30
Virginia Tanedo-Garcia Elementary School	36
Pangí Elementary School	31
TOTAL	194

Instruments

The researcher used one instrument to conduct this study. It is adapted and modified from the study of Saavedra (2020) entitled Factors that Contribute to the Poor Writing Skills in Filipino and English of the Elementary Pupils. It has three indicators: spelling skills, writing skills, and grammar skills. Each indicator is composed of five statement items.

In evaluating the English proficiency level of Grade 1 learners, the following scales were used:

<i>Range of Means</i>	<i>Level</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>
4.50-5.00	Very High	It means that the English proficiency level is very high
3.50-4.49	High	It means that the English proficiency level is high
2.50-3.49	Moderately High	It means that the English proficiency level is moderately high
1.50-2.49	Low	It means that the English proficiency level is low
1.0-1.49	Very Low	It means that the English proficiency level is very low

Expert validators thoroughly validated the instrument. Based on their suggestions and recommendations, the instrument was subjected to various revisions before the expert validators approved it. Research instrument validation is essential in ensuring the reliability and validity of data collected through surveys, questionnaires, or other measurement tools. It involves assessing the quality and accuracy of the instrument to ensure that it measures what it intends to measure (Aithal & Aithal, 2020).

Data Collection

To pursue this study, the researcher collected data from the book of Elsayed and Elsayed (2021) entitled "Fundamental of Research Methodology and Data Collection." The researcher made a research questionnaire and asked expert validators to validate the instrument. Then, the researcher asked permission from the Ethics and Review Committee and the Graduate School. Upon the approval of the request, the researcher asked permission to conduct the study from the office of the Schools Division Superintendent, Schools Division Office of the Division of Sarangani. Then, the received copy was brought to the school heads where the study was conducted.

Moreover, the researcher prepared the questionnaire for reproduction according to the number of target respondents. After reproducing the questionnaire, the researcher personally explained the Informed Consent Form (ICF) and administered it to the respondents. They were given ample time to complete the questionnaires. Then, while retrieving the questionnaires, the researcher checked if the respondents had accomplished all the items. Finally, the completed questionnaires were summarized, tallied, analyzed, and interpreted.

Statistical Tools

The following statistical tools were utilized to treat the gathered data:

Mean. It was used to determine the reading proficiency level of Grade 1 learners in East Maitum District in answer to objective 1.

Frequency Count and Percentage. It was used to determine the academic performance of Grade learners in answer to objective 2.

Pearson's r. It was used to examine the relationship between dependent and multiple independent variables to answer objective 3.

Regression Analysis. It was used to determine which domain of English proficiency level predicted the academic performance of Grade 1 learners in answer to objective 4.

Ethical Considerations

Significant ethical issues played a vital role in gathering data. The ethical considerations in this research were concerned with the proper conduct of the study, confidentiality, and anonymity. The RMMC Ethics and Review Committee's requirements for ethical consideration were adhered to in this study, especially when dealing with the participants and the data, including but not limited to the following:

Voluntary Participation. The respondents were allowed to participate without any plan of repercussion, reparations, or loss of benefits. Following the respondent's explanation of the study's objective, the respondent's rights to contribute to the body of knowledge were carefully considered and anticipated. The respondents in this study were not coerced into taking part. If people got uncomfortable while participating in the study, they could stop.

Privacy and confidentiality. Respondents' privacy rights were not violated without their informed agreement under the Data Privacy Act of 2012, which safeguards this fundamental human right. Allowing respondents to omit their names from the survey questionnaire was one technique to maintain privacy and confidentiality in this quantitative study. In addition, confidentiality and privacy were preserved by withholding the informants' personal information, such as their age, gender, occupation, and health conditions. As a result, their identity was kept private for security reasons. Their answers to the survey questionnaire were kept confidential and treated as such.

Informed consent process. Given the limitations of the inquiry, potential research volunteers were fully informed of the study's goals, methods, and rewards in the most detailed way conceivable. The fact that the respondents' permission was requested demonstrated that their participation was freely given. It provided respondents with the necessary information and discussed the survey's methodology. The informed consent form required respondents to sign to indicate that they freely chose to participate in the study. The respondents' identities were not listed on the survey form, and their responses were kept private. The respondents knew they could withdraw from participating in the study at anytime.

Recruitment. The respondents were informed of why they had become part of the study. The researcher provided an explanation of the study's goal to facilitate additional inferences and enable the respondents to grasp the substance of the study. In addition to the letter, the researcher explained the relevance and reasoning for the study.

Risks. Research was conducted to determine if there was an acceptable positive benefit-risk ratio. This study's need to protect the respondents from significant harm is equally essential. The study prioritized the welfare of the respondents. Furthermore, the respondents were not harmed since their identity was held confidential. Their security and safety were of the utmost concern. As the researcher, I needed to ensure that the respondents were physically, emotionally, and socially ready. In answering the survey questionnaire, the researcher provided the respondents did not feel discomfort or awkwardness.

Benefits. This study hoped to provide significance globally by providing valuable insights into the distribution, trends, and patterns of English proficiency worldwide, allowing for a better understanding of individuals' and communities' linguistic capabilities and needs. This study identified the factors contributing to language skill disparities and explored ways to bridge the gap, fostering more significant social and economic equity. Moreover, the results of this study may benefit the Department of Education by creating an intervention program as a reference in formulating school policies and programs that may aid the teachers, parents, and learners in enriching their English proficiency skills. On the other hand, this study may help teachers with the necessary approaches to guide learners in improving their reading skills by focusing on writing skills. The study may guide the community in formulating policies, plans, programs, projects, activities, and other reforms for the reading program in the new normal. The study can be used as the basis for further studies on the reading proficiency level of learners. Other researchers who wished to undertake similar development studies may find this a good source of information.

Plagiarism. There was no hint or proof that the research had misinterpreted someone else's work. Grammarly software and other plagiarism checkers were used in the study. The integrity and good character of the researcher are linked to moral principles and ideals. To produce a respectable research report, the researcher must be more knowledgeable about plagiarism.

Fabrication. The report did not hint or provide evidence that the work had been intentionally misinterpreted. There was no fabrication of information or outcomes or deliberate presentation of incorrect conclusions. The investigator utilized and incorporated ideas associated with the data and other inferential notions.

Falsification. The study did not purposefully misrepresent the work to fit a model or theoretical expectation and had no evidence of

overclaiming or exaggeration. Additionally, this study needed to follow the practices of data manipulation, which include making claims based on incomplete information or omitting crucial elements, as well as using materials, instruments, or procedures that might mislead others.

Conflict of Interest (COI). There were no signs of a conflict of interest in the study, including disclosing one. A conflict of interest is a collection of situations in which a professional's assessment of a primary interest—such as participant welfare or the validity of the research—is likely to be impacted by a secondary interest—such as financial or academic gains or recognitions. In addition, the respondents were coerced into participating in the study by the researcher, who lacked any power or sway over them.

Deceit. The study did not mislead the respondents about any possible danger. Since research participants have completed higher education, their rights must be enormously safeguarded, and acceptable and balanced guidelines must be followed.

Permission from Organization/Location. The study's researcher adhered to procedures. Following the go-ahead from the panels, advisor, and RMMC ERC committee, the researcher formally requested permission from the superintendents of the school divisions to conduct the study through a letter. Following this, the researcher composed an official letter and attached the school's letter of support from the school division's superintendent to the District Supervisor and Principal of the participating schools in the study.

Authorship. Ethical authorship ensures that all individuals who contributed substantially to the research were appropriately acknowledged as authors. In contrast, those who did not meet the criteria for authorship were not included. The researcher ensured that the study's results appropriately reflected the contributions of all parties involved and were fair and transparent. Research outputs maintained their credibility and made a fair and transparent contribution to the progress of knowledge by abiding by ethical authoring norms.

Results

This section deals with the presentation, analysis, and interpretation of the data gathered in the study.

3.1. The Level of English Proficiency Among Grade 1 Learners

Table 2 presents the data on the level of English proficiency in terms of spelling, writing, and grammar skills. Mean was utilized to treat the gathered data.

Based on the data analysis, the level of English proficiency was high, with an average mean of 3.5. Spelling skills were high, with a mean score of 3.6. It indicated that learners can spell 3-letter words correctly in writing, spell three and 4-letter words orally, demonstrate knowledge of spelling words with silent letters, spell 4-letter words accurately in writing, and correctly spell words with prefixes and suffixes. It suggests a strong competence in spelling skills, reflecting learners' proficiency in various aspects of spelling within the English language.

Further, the level of English proficiency in terms of writing skills was found to be high, with a mean score of 3.6. It indicated that learners demonstrate competence in various aspects of writing. They can write the alphabet correctly, utilize accurate punctuation marks, employ capital letters appropriately, write quickly and accurately, and effectively write numerical numbers from 1 to 100. These findings suggest that learners have a firm grasp of writing skills, encompassing key elements such as alphabet formation, punctuation, capitalization, writing fluency, and numerical representation.

Furthermore, the level of proficiency in grammar skills was moderately high, as reflected by a mean score of 3.4. It suggests that learners sometimes demonstrate agreement in certain aspects of grammar. They can use correct basic sentence structure, employ present and past tenses accurately, correctly utilize singular and plural nouns, and appropriately apply articles (a, an, the). While there is room for improvement, learners show a solid foundation in these fundamental grammar skills.

Table 2. *The Level of English Proficiency Among Grade 1 Learners*

<i>A. Spelling Skill</i>	<i>Mean n=194</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. I can spell 3-letter words correctly when I write.	3.0	High
2. I can spell three and 4-letter words orally.	3.5	High
3. I can spell words with silent letters.	3.4	High
4. I can spell 4-letter words correctly when I write.	3.6	High
5. I can spell words with prefixes and suffixes correctly.	3.8	High
TOTAL	3.6	High
<i>B. Writing Skill</i>		
1. I can write the alphabet correctly.	3.7	High
2. I can write accurate punctuation marks.	3.6	High
3. I can use capital letters correctly when I write.	3.7	High
4. I can write quickly with less error.	3.5	High
5. I can write numerical numbers from 1-100.	3.5	High
TOTAL	3.6	High
<i>C. Grammar Skill</i>		

1. I can use the correct basic sentence structure.	3.5	High
2. I can use present tenses correctly.	3.0	High
3. I can use past tenses correctly.	3.5	High
4. I can use singular and plural nouns correctly.	3.6	High
5. I can use articles correctly. (a, an, the)	3.5	High
Total	3.4	Moderately High
Average Mean	3.6	High

3.2. The Level of Academic Performance of Learners

Table 3 presents the data on the level of academic performance of Grade 1 learners.

Data revealed that 39 or 20%, attained an outstanding academic performance, meaning learners obtained 90 to 100 grades. 81, or 42%, obtained a very satisfactory academic performance. 54, or 28%, obtained a satisfactory academic performance. 20, or 10%, obtained a fairly satisfactory academic performance. All of the learners met expectations.

Table 3. *The Level of Academic Performance of Learners*

Description	Frequency n=161	Percentage
Outstanding (90-100)	39	30
Very Satisfactory (85-89)	81	42
Satisfactory (80-84)	54	29
Fairly Satisfactory (75-79)	20	10
Did Not Meet Expectations (75 and below)	0	0
Total	184	180

3.3. Significant Relationship between English Proficiency Level and Academic Performance of Grade 1 Learners

Table 4 presents the significant relationship between English proficiency level and the academic performance of Grade 1 learners. Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation was used to treat the data gathered.

According to the examination of the link between factors, a substantial correlation has been found between the learner's academic self-efficacy and performance. It suggests that a learner's academic achievement is related to their level of English proficiency. It was discovered that the data were tested at the Alpha level.05 with a df of 159 when the learner's academic achievement and English proficiency levels were compared. The calculated Pearson's Product Moment Coefficient of Correlation value was 0.79, as the table demonstrates. In comparison to the tabular value of 0.170, it was more significant. As a result, the null hypothesis was rejected. The level of English proficiency significantly influenced the learner's academic performance.

Table 4. *Significant Relationship between English Proficiency Level and Academic Performance of Grade 1 Learners*

Variables	Df	rxy value		Decision	Analysis
		Computed	Tabular		
English Proficiency Level vs. Learner's Academic Performance	159	0.79	0.170	Reject null hypothesis	There was a significant relationship

3.4. The Domain that Predicts the Academic Performance of Grade 1 Learners

The data revealed that spelling and writing skills significantly predicted the academic performance of Grade 1 learners since the probability value is $p < 0.05$. R² value of .409 implied that 40.9% of the English proficiency predicted the academic performance of Grade 1 learners, while other factors influenced the remaining 59.1%. It revealed that the t-values of English proficiency in terms of spelling, writing, and grammar skills were 2.13, 3.306, and 1.017, respectively.

Therefore, the 3 indicators in English proficiency, spelling and writing skills significantly predicted the academic performance of Grade 1. However, the best domain that significantly predicted learners' academic performance was applied performance, with a coefficient of .201 and $p = .004$ and a coefficient of .252 and $p = .003$, which is less than a 0.05 significance level.

Table 5. *The Domain that Predicts the Academic Performance of Grade 1 Learners*

English Proficiency	Academic Proficiency		
	B	t-value	p-value
Spelling Skills	.201	2.13	.004
Writing Skills	.252	3.306	.003
Grammar Skills	.071	1.017	.306
R	.628		
R-square	.409		
F-value	101.09		
P-value	.000		

Discussion

This section presents the conclusions and recommendations based on the data gathered.

The Level of English Proficiency Among Grade 1 Learners

Learners' English proficiency level was high in spelling and writing skills and moderately high in grammar.

A high spelling skill indicated that learners could consistently and accurately write words without making spelling errors. This assumption paralleled the study of Carlson (2020), who asserted that practical spelling skills are developed through explicit instruction, practice, and exposure to a wide range of words. Explicit instruction involves teaching learners the rules and conventions of spelling and common patterns and strategies for remembering how to spell words. Exposure to a wide range of words is significant because it enables learners to develop a more robust mental lexicon, which helps them to recognize and remember words more easily. Learners can improve their communication and academic performance by developing practical spelling skills.

Moreover, a high level of writing skills indicated that learners could communicate effectively through the written word. According to Widiyaningsih et al., (2019), writing is a powerful tool for communication and self-expression. Good writing skills are essential in both personal and professional contexts. To develop good writing skills, it is essential to understand the purpose of the writing, identify the target audience, and choose an appropriate writing style.

Furthermore, moderately high grammar skills indicated that learners possessed a reasonably strong understanding and proficiency but may only be considered somewhat experts. In the study of Putri & Education (2022), grammar is the set of rules that govern the structure of a language. Good grammar skills are essential for effective communication, both written and spoken. Proper grammar ensures that the meaning of a sentence is unambiguous. It also helps to convey professionalism and credibility, particularly in professional or academic settings. It is essential to understand the basic grammar rules, such as subject-verb agreement, proper punctuation, and correct use of pronouns to improve grammar skills.

The Level of Academic Performance of Learners

Most learners obtained very satisfactory academic performance, indicating that their grades were significantly above average which met or exceeded expectations. Aithal and Aithal (2020) stated that academic performance measures student achievement across various subjects. Typically, educators use classroom performance, graduation rates, and test scores to gauge student accomplishment. Students' learning abilities, family background, peer pressure, teacher quality, and learning infrastructure all impact their academic achievement. State and federal education authorities gather graduation rates as a standard indicator of secondary school success. Every state administers exams to students at the elementary, middle, and high school levels each year to gauge their subject-matter ability.

Significant Relationship between English Proficiency Level and Academic Performance of Grade 1 Learners

According to the examination of the link between factors, a substantial correlation had been found between the learner's academic self-efficacy and performance. It implies that the English proficiency level is associated with the learner's academic performance. The relationship analysis between variables indicated a significant correlation between a learner's academic self-efficacy and performance. It suggested that learners with higher confidence in their abilities perform better academically. Furthermore, this relationship extended to English proficiency, implying that a learner's level of proficiency in English is also linked to their overall academic performance. In other words, learners who are more proficient in English will likely achieve higher academic success. This finding underscored the importance of fostering academic self-efficacy and English language skills to enhance the overall academic outcomes.

According to Pan et al. (2021), this association is particularly relevant in educational settings where English is the primary medium of instruction, as it suggests that individuals with strong English language skills tend to perform better academically. Such individuals are better equipped to comprehend instructional material, communicate effectively, and demonstrate their knowledge and understanding of English, contributing to improved academic results. This enhanced comprehension and communication capability directly contribute to their academic success. For example, students proficient in English can better grasp complex concepts presented in textbooks, follow lectures more efficiently, and engage in meaningful interactions with peers and instructors. Furthermore, their ability to articulate their understanding and responses in assessments and assignments in English helps them perform well academically.

The Domain that Predicts the Academic Performance of Grade 1 Learners

Among the 3 indicators in English proficiency, spelling and writing skills significantly predicted the academic performance of Grade 1. However, the best domain that significantly predicts learners' academic performance was applied performance, with a coefficient of .201 and $p = .004$ and a coefficient of .252 and $p = .003$, which is less than a 0.05 significance level.

This assumption is supported by the study by Dębska et al. (2019), which states that the domain of vocabulary, writing, and spelling skills can serve as significant predictors of a learner's academic performance. Proficiency in vocabulary involves a wide range of words and their meanings, enabling students to comprehend texts, express ideas clearly, and demonstrate comprehension in various subjects. A rich vocabulary facilitates adequate reading comprehension, critical thinking, and communication skills, all essential for success across academic disciplines. Strong writing skills contribute to academic performance by enabling students to effectively convey their

thoughts, analyze information, and express arguments coherently.

Conclusion

The following conclusions were established and formulated based on the results of the study: First, the level of English proficiency of learners was high in terms of spelling and writing skills while moderately high in terms of grammar skills. Second, most learners obtained satisfactory academic performance in their writing skills. Third, a significant relationship existed between learners' English proficiency and academic performance. Lastly, the best domains that predicted the academic performance of Grade 1 was applied performance.

Based on the study's results, the following recommendations were established: The Department of Education may enhance the educational plan by embedding dedicated grammar instruction into the curriculum, providing students with a thorough understanding of grammar rules and concepts. To address poor English proficiency, it may consider implementing a comprehensive approach to address the poor English proficiency level of Grade 1 learners. This approach may include increased investment in early childhood education programs emphasizing English language acquisition, training for teachers in effective language teaching methods, the development of age-appropriate and culturally relevant English-language learning materials, and ongoing assessment and support to identify and assist struggling learners. Moreover, fostering a positive and supportive learning environment that encourages regular English language practice inside and outside the classroom may significantly enhance Grade 1 learners' English proficiency.

Moreover, school administrators may provide professional development by offering teachers opportunities for professional development to enhance their knowledge and teaching strategies in grammar instruction. Further, school heads may promote the utilization of technology by integrating technology-based tools, such as grammar-checking software and online resources, to provide additional support and valuable practice opportunities. Finally, teachers may cultivate motivation toward learners by fostering a good learning environment that promotes active participation in grammar studies and highlighting the significance of grammar for successful communication.

Furthermore, to address the lowest domain that predicted learners' academic performance, the Department of Education, together with school administrators and school heads, may conduct specialized writing workshops or classes on a range of writing topics, including essay production, sentence construction, paragraph development, and grammar. These workshops can provide learners with concentrated instruction and practice.

Teachers may also provide learners with constructive, personalized feedback on their writing. Please encourage them to revise and improve their work based on this feedback. It can be done by teachers, peers, or through self-assessment.

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